

TESHIKTOSH (ANDIJON VILOYATI) ADIR FLORASI BO'YICHA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN TAHLIL NATIJALARI

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Kirish. So'ngi yillarda aholi turar joylarining kengayishi, urbanizatsiya darajasini ortishi, iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarini jadal suratlar bilan rivojlanib borishi biologik xilma-xillikning qisqarishiga sabab bo'lmoqda (1-rasm). Bugungi kunda, O'zbekiston hududining 82% tabiiy landshafti antropogen omillar ta'siriga uchragan, 18% esa to'liq o'zlashtirilgan [1]. Farg'ona vodiysi esa yaylov maydonlariga bo'lgan talabning ortishi, chorvachilikning kengayishi va aholi sonining (1 km² 300-400 kishi) o'sib borishi [2] sababli tabiiy landshafti qisqarib borayotgan hududlardan biri sifatida etirof etiladi [3].

1-Rasm. Tadqiqot hududi

So'ngi o'tgan davr muobaynida Farg'ona vodiysi bo'ylab ko'plab floristik va sistematik tadqiqotlar F.Karimov, [4], G.Ibrohimova [5] va X.Xoshimov [6] va boshqalar tomonida amalga oshirilgan. Ammo Andijon viloyatida joylashgan Teshiktosh adirlari va ularda tarqalgan o'simlik turlari alohida maqsadli tadqiqotlar olib borilmagan va hududni tur tarkibi bo'yicha zamonaviy ma'lumotlar yetishmaydi. Shu sababli Teshiktosh viloyati Teshiktosh adirlarini tur tarkibini aniqlash va tahlillarini amalga oshirish birlamchi maqsad sifatida belgilandi.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi. Teshiktosh adirlarida tarqalgan va O'zbekiston milliy gerbariyasida (TASH) saqlanayotgan gerbariy namunalaridagi manzillar koordinatalari Google Earth 7.1v dasturi orqali olindi. Taksonlarning nomenklaturasi Plants of the World Online [7] va International Plant Name Index [8] xalqaro katalogi bo'yicha keltirildi. Qo'riqlanadigan hududlar tahlili [9] hamda bioxima-xillik markazlari to'qrisida ma'lumotlar [10] mavjud manbalar asosida keltirildi.

Natijalar va tahlillar. 2023-2024 yillar davomida Farg'ona vodiysining Andijon va Farg'ona viloyatlarida maqsadli floristik tur tarkibini aniqlash? To'rt tizimli xaritalarini yaratish bo'yicha Namangan davlat universiteti Biologiya kafedrasida botanik olimlari tomonidan tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda.

Ta'kidlash lozimki Tog'li O'rta Osiyo provinsiyasi dunyodagi 36 (KBA: Biologik xilma-xillik to'g'risidagi konvensiya) bioxilma-xillik qaynoq nuqtasining biri hisoblanadi. Mazkur hududda 142 taga yaqin bioxilma-xillik markazlari mavjud. Ularni 40 ga yaqini Farg'ona vodiysini tabiiy geografik hududida joylashgan [10]. Mazkur hududlarning biri sifatida Teshiktosh adirlari etirof etiladi. Tahlil natijasiga ko'ra Teshiktosh adirlarida va unga yondosh hududlarda 9 ta oilaga mansub 24 tur o'simliklar uchirishi aniqlandi. Ular 1-jadvalda keltirildi.

1-Jadval

Andijon viloyati Teshiktosh adirlarida tarqalgan o'simlik turlari

№	Oila	Turlar
1	Asteraceae Bercht. & J.Presl	<i>Achillea biebersteinii</i> C.Afan, <i>Artemisia tenuisecta</i> Nevski, <i>Sonchus asper</i> (L.) Hill, <i>Taraxacum contristans</i> Kovalevsk, <i>Taraxacum longipyramidatum</i> Schischk, <i>Taraxacum reflexum</i> Schischk.
2	Brassicaceae Burnett	<i>Crambe Kotschyana</i> Boiss, <i>Erysimum gypsaceum</i> Botsch. et Vved, <i>Megacarpaea orbiculata</i> B. Fedtsch.
3	Cannabaceae Martinov	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.
4	Amaranthaceae Juss.	<i>Atriplex flabellum</i> Bunge, <i>Salsola drobovii</i>
5	Euphorbiaceae Juss.	<i>Euphorbia jaxartica</i> Prokh.
6	Fabaceae Lindl.	<i>Lotus sergievskiae</i> Kamelin et Kovalevsk, <i>Medicago sativa</i> L., <i>Sphaerophysa salsula</i> (Pall.) DC.Prodr, <i>Trifolium repens</i> L., <i>Trigonella orthoceras</i> Kar. et Kir., <i>Vicia angustifolia</i>
7	Geraniaceae Juss.	<i>Geranium transversale</i> (Benth.)
8	Lamiaceae Martinov	<i>Lallemantia royleana</i> (Benth.), <i>Mentha longifolia</i> var. <i>asiatica</i> (Boriss.) Rech.f, <i>Perovskia scrophulariefolia</i> Bunge.
9	Liliaceae Juss.	<i>Tulipa ferganica</i> Vved,

So'ngi yillarda Teshiktosh adirlari insonlar tomonidan faol o'zlashtirib kelinmoqda. Mazkur hududda keng tarqalgan turlar bilan birga noyob turlar ham tarqalgan. Ularga *Tulipa ferganica* Vved., *Salsola drobovii* Botsch. kabi turlarni olish mumkin.

Oilalar bo'yicha statistik tahlili natijasiga ko'ra Asteraceae va Fabaceae oila vakillari ustun qilishi aniqlandi. Qolgan oilalar past ko'rsatkichni egalladi. Kamyob turlarga ega oilalar sifatida Liliaceae va Amaranthaceae oilalari muhim ahamiyatga ega hissoylanadi.

2-Rasm. Teshiktosh adirlarida tarqalgan o'simlik oilalarini taqsimot diagrammasi

Xulosa. Teshiktosh adirlar florasi birlamchi adabiyot tahlili va gerbariy fondlarda saqlanayotgan ma'lumotlar asosida tahlil etildi. Natijada hududning birlamchi tur tarkibi shakllantirildi. Ular 9 oilaga mansub 24 turdan iborat bo'lib, Asteraceae va Fabaceae oila vakillari ustunlik qilishi aniqlandi.

2024 yil hudud bo'ylab maqsadli dala tadqiqotlarini o'tkazish, antropogen ta'sirini baholash uchun navbatdagi amaliy tadqiqotlar o'tkazish rejalashtirilgan.

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